

Speculation on Entropy in Terms of a Maximum Number of Measurements

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In (1), it is noted that there is a difference between information entropy and thermodynamic entropy which appears in the first law of thermodynamics. In particular, the authors of (1) consider a single particle at rest somewhere in a box of length L (one dimension). It is argued that the particle is either to the right of the center line or to the left. If one compresses the box from the right to $L/2$ and the particle is not found, then no work is done and (1) argues that thermodynamic entropy is 0. If the particle is on the right hand side, work is done "to overcome inertia", but (1) argues that this is not thermodynamic work and so $S=0$ again and $dV=0$. It is stated that "there can be no general statement between information and thermodynamic entropy" (1).

In this note, we try to consider entropy in terms of the \ln of the maximum number of measurements required to determine the state of a single particle. We apply this both to the thermodynamic ideal gas case for which the first law of thermodynamics applies and to the scenario of a single particle in a box and argue that there does seem to be a link between the two using this definition, at least for the case of an ideal gas. (In other words, Shannon's entropy, which is also thermodynamical entropy, applies to an ideal gas.)

First Law of Thermodynamics and an Ideal Gas

An ideal gas is one for which $E(\text{energy})= 3/2 N RT$ ((1)), where N is the number of particles and T , temperature. The first law of thermodynamics may first be written as an energy conservation law:

$$dE = \delta Q + \delta W \quad \text{where } Q \text{ is heat and } W \text{ work } ((2))$$

with $W = -P dV$ (P =pressure, V =volume) ((3)). Heat is energy which does not involve changing V , but is more complicated than just that and must be further clarified. If one has a box with a gas, one may add a large mass to it without changing its volume, hence no work is done, but energy E changes. There is no extra heat, however. Heat flow seems to mean that the average kinetic energy of the gas molecules changes while volume V remains constant. If the average kinetic energy changes then T (temperature), which is defined a such, changes. A change in T , however, does not necessarily mean a heat flow even though $E=3/2NRT$ changes for an ideal gas. It is possible to have no heat flow which means that:

$$dE = -PdV ((3))$$

The ideal gas, however, changes volume (shrinks) and it heats (T increases) because of the work given to it. The combined effect means no heat flow. Thus, surprisingly perhaps, heat flow is not simply measured by T for an ideal gas, but by T and V for N =constant.

Specifically, the Sackur-Tetrode equation for an ideal gas is (2):

S proportional to $\ln \{ V (T \text{ power } 3/2) \}$ ((3))

A decrease in V means a decrease in S and an increase in T means an increase in S . A decrease in V may offset an increase in T and leave $dS = 0$ with

Delta heat $\rightarrow T dS$ ((4))

We ask: How does one associate entropy with probability? Traditionally from Boltzmann, one considers \ln of the number of states a particle may reside in in phase space (p,r) . Here we wish to consider entropy in terms of the maximum number of measurements needed to determine the state of a single particle in a system. To do so, we first consider the scenario of (1) in which one has a single particle at rest in a box (1-dimension) of length L .

Particle at Rest in a Box of Length L

In (1), a particle is considered to be at rest in a box of length L and is said to be either to the left or right of the center line. If the box is compressed from the right and the particle is not found, (1) states that no work is done, but that thermodynamic entropy is 0. If, on the other hand, the particle is found, work is done overcoming its inertia, but it is stated that this is not thermodynamic work and that $dV=0$ and $S=0$. (1) argues that there are two kinds of entropy, thermodynamic and informational and that there is no general relation between the two. In other words, Shannon's entropy may change, but this does not mean that thermodynamic entropy does.

Here we try to find a consistent scheme for viewing the particle in a box with an ideal gas. We suggest that one consider the \ln of the maximum number of measurements required to find the single particle at rest in a box. This approach also works for a particle moving at constant speed as will be discussed.

To find the maximum number of measurements needed to find a particle at rest in a box of length L , consider the particle to be at the left hand edge of the box and start measuring x,t from the right by compressing the box. Thus, once an x measurement is made, this x value is no longer available to the particle. The maximum number of measurements is proportional to L . Once a measurement finds the particle, its x,t are known. Given that it is at rest it has the same x for all t . If the particle is moving with constant v and one assumes that the measurement involves moving the wall from the right to the left, then if the particle contacts the wall, it reflects with $-v$ at a certain x,t (assuming the wall moves at almost 0 speed and one may compute its exact trajectory and so all uncertainty is gone. Thus, information entropy, which we defines as proportional to

$\ln(\text{maximum number of measurements})$ ((4))

becomes 0 as soon as contact is made with either a moving or stationary single mass. If contact is not made, then the remaining constrained length L/b is proportional to the maximum number of remaining measurements which must be made. Thus, if one stops measuring when the box is at $x=L/2$, then the information entropy is proportional to $\ln(L/2)$.

The question is now whether this definition may be applied to the thermodynamic entropy of an ideal gas.

Thermodynamic Entropy of an Ideal Gas and $\ln(\text{maximum number of measurements})$

The thermodynamic entropy of an ideal gas is given by ((3)) which contains $\ln(V) + \ln(T^{3/2})$. $\ln(V)$ is equivalent $\ln(L)$ in one dimension and is consistent with the $\ln(\text{maximum number of measurements})$ where in this case, the measurement is of x . A particle in an ideal gas, however, is not simply defined by its x,y,z position, but also by its internal kinetic energy (nonrelativistically and classically). One needs a number proportional to L as the maximum number of position measurements. Average energy per particle is $3/2 RT$. In order that:

$$dE = -PdV \quad \text{for no heat flow} \quad ((5))$$

and $\delta \text{ heat flow} \rightarrow T dS$, one has using $\ln(L)$: $0 = T (dL/L + \text{function } dT)$ ((6))

At the same time, for $dV=0$, one has: $dE = 3/2 N R dT = T \text{ function } dT$.

Thus, $\text{function } dT = 3/2 NR dT/T$.

This leads to: $\ln(T^{3/2})$ as the entropy piece linked with T . For an ideal gas there are two considerations of entropy. One must consider a maximum number of measurements to find x and another to find e . A product is used: $(\text{maximum number of position measurements}) * (\text{maximum number of energy measurements})$ because any space measurement i may find x , while the corresponding energy measurement which finds e may be j .

In the case of length, or volume, it is straightforward to argue that L or V represents the maximum number of measurements required to find a specific x or (x,y,z)

In the case of energy, statistical mechanical texts (3) suggest that the number of states is proportional to E^f , where $f=3/2$ in three dimensions. Thus, this represents the maximum number of measurements required. We thus suggest that the notion of information entropy is present in the concept of a thermodynamic entropy, at least for an ideal gas.

Why $\ln(\text{maximum number of measurement})$ as Entropy?

If one has a single particle in a box and it moves with constant v , then its equation of motion is: $x=vt +B$, where B depends on the initial conditions. The only unknown is B regardless of the size of the box. One might argue that B represents the only uncertainty in the problem and is independent of the size of the box, which has nothing to do with an initial condition. The problem is that to find B one must measure space to find the particle at a certain x,t set. If space is restricted (by the volume of the box) fewer maximum number of measurements are required. Thus, entropy seems to be directly related to the maximum number of measurements needed and not simply the unknown B .

Case of a Toss of a Coin

Shannon's entropy (information entropy) exists for the toss of a coin, even though there are no energy considerations needed and hence no need for the first law of thermodynamics. In the first law of thermodynamics, delta heat deals with energy which is not linked to changing volume V (or some other global constraint parameter). We have argued above, however, that this does not mean that one may only associate T with delta heat. One requires V as well. T is linked with single particle average energy $3/2 RT$ and so we argue that V and T are both linked with probability and that this is an informational probability, at least in the case of V for no potential $V(x)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that for the case of an ideal gas at least, there seems to be a link between thermodynamic entropy and informational entropy. We suggest that one consider entropy as $\ln(\text{maximum number of measurements})$ needed to find a particular value of a single particle. In the case of an ideal gas, one needs to find both (x,y,x) and e and so one has a product of maximum number of measurements for each. In both cases, the maximum number of measurements is linked to overall average constraints of V and E as T power $3/2$, for e , follows from $E = 3/2 NRT$ as shown.

References

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